

DIRECTIONS OF WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY. PROCESSES OF PSYCHOPHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN THEM

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This article is devoted to directions for working with children with cerebral palsy. It shows how to treat children and study their mental experience.

Keywords: cerebral palsy, CP, psychophysical development, atypical oligophrenia, mental retardation, mental illness, activation.

Children with musculoskeletal disorders usually include children with cerebral palsy. Cerebral palsy is a group of motor disorders caused by damage to the motor areas and motor pathways of the brain. The main feature in cerebral palsy is the presence of motor disorders from birth and their close connection with emotional disorders. Due to various degrees of motor disorders of the child, he is completely dependent on adults from birth. This negatively affects the child's emotional sphere, he lacks initiative and develops passivity in actions. A feature of mental development with cerebral palsy is not only its slow pace, but also its uneven nature, the acceleration of the development of some functions and the lag behind others. Violation of attention and memory is manifested in increased distraction, inability to concentrate for a long time, narrowness of its volume, predominance of verbal memory over visual and tactile memory. Distortion of space gnosis: it is manifested in the slow formation of concepts that determine the position of objects and parts of one's body in space, the inability to recognize and repeat geometric shapes, adding a whole from parts. Intellectual development of children with cerebral palsy may be preserved, but slightly reduced. According to E.S. Kalizhniuk, children with cerebral palsy can be divided into two groups depending on the level of mental retardation. (mental retardation and atypical oligophrenia). Children with cerebral palsy are characterized by the underdevelopment of the highest forms of mental activity - abstract thinking.

Typical manifestations of speech disorders in such children are various disorders of the vocal pronunciation side of speech. Therefore, the speech of these children is unclear and not very understandable to others. The severity of the violation of the voice pronunciation side of speech increases with breathing disorders: speech exhalation is shortened, the child breathes separately during speech, speech loses its smoothness and expressiveness. Psychological rehabilitation in cerebral palsy includes a system of special measures aimed at restoring (developing, forming) mental functions, processes, characteristics,

abilities that allow the child to master and perform various actions. aimed at restoring (developing) social roles, adaptation in society, that is, psychological mechanisms of social integration.

The system of psychological rehabilitation consists of the following components: psychodiagnosis, psychocorrection, psychological support and referral to a psychological profession. The expediency of psychological rehabilitation, its priorities, optimal methodical techniques are determined primarily by which areas of mental activity are disturbed and which mental functions should be restored and developed first of all. This requires a psychodiagnostic examination. Psychodiagnostics allows to determine the current mental state and characteristics of potential mental development (zone of proximal development) of a child with cerebral palsy. In the process of psychological diagnosis of children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, a number of basic principles should be followed (R. Ya. Abromovich-Lichtman, 1965);

1. The principle of activity aimed at conducting a psychological examination in the context of the activity of a child with cerebral palsy: subject-practical, game, education.

2. The principle of qualitative analysis of data obtained from psychological

3. The principle of a personal approach in the diagnostic process, the psychologist analyzes not a single symptom, but the whole child's personality.

4. The principle of the comparative approach in the study of developmental disorders, the psychologist should be correctly oriented to the specific characteristics of the mental development of a healthy child.

5. The principle of a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis of mental development of a child includes taking into account many factors that cause disorders in the development of a child with cerebral palsy: clinical, pedagogical, psychological, social.

According to the results of psychodiagnostics, there should be:

- identified mental illnesses, mechanisms for determining their rehabilitation prospects;

- the most impaired mental functions were identified in order to "activate" compensatory mechanisms, which is very important, especially when the impaired function cannot be restored;

- assessment of the characteristics of mental activity that helps the child's successful social integration at various stages of youth development was carried out. Directions for working with children with cerebral palsy. Organization of work with parents of children with cerebral palsy. Psychophysical development of children with CP

The main feature in cerebral palsy is the presence of motor disorders from birth and their close connection with emotional disorders. Due to various degrees of motor disorders of the child, he is completely dependent on adults from birth. This negatively affects the child's emotional sphere, he lacks initiative and develops passivity in actions. A feature of mental development with cerebral palsy is not only its slow pace, but also its uneven nature, the acceleration of the development of some functions and the lag behind others. Violation of attention and memory is manifested in increased distraction, inability to concentrate for a long time, narrowness of its volume, predominance of verbal memory over visual and tactile memory. Distortion of space gnosis: it is manifested in the slow formation of concepts that determine the position of objects and parts of one's body in space, the inability to recognize and repeat geometric shapes, adding a whole from parts.

Intellectual development of children with cerebral palsy may be preserved, but slightly reduced. According to E.S. Kalizhniuk, children with cerebral palsy can be divided into two groups depending on the level of mental retardation. (mental retardation and atypical oligophrenia). Children with cerebral palsy are characterized by the underdevelopment of the highest forms of mental activity - abstract thinking. Typical manifestations of speech disorders in such children are various disorders of the vocal pronunciation side of speech. Therefore, the speech of these children is unclear and not very understandable to others. The severity of the violation of the voice pronunciation side of speech increases with breathing disorders: speech exhalation is shortened, the child breathes separately during speech, speech loses its smoothness and expressiveness.

Almost all children with cerebral palsy are tired. With purposeful actions that require the participation of thought processes, they become lethargic faster than their healthy peers, it is difficult for them to concentrate on the task. If they cannot complete the task, they may refuse to complete it and lose interest in it altogether. Personal development in children with cerebral palsy has its own characteristics. Emotional disturbances are manifested in the form of increased excitability, a tendency to mood swings, and the appearance of fear. Mood swings are often combined with inert emotional responses. So the child starts to cry or laugh, he can't stop. Increased emotional arousal is often combined with tearfulness, irritability, moodiness, discontent reactions, which increase in a new environment for the child and with fatigue. An important developmental factor is also the child's perception of himself as part of a community engaged in useful work. Children are always interested in activities that bring great benefit to the

community and practical benefits... This encourages them to engage in various types of socially useful work.

Children with cerebral palsy are very sensitive to the attitude of others towards them and react to any changes in their behavior. Such children are very impressionable, they are easily offended, the reason for their displeasure or any negative reaction. Using the Pertra playset in working with preschool children Preschool childhood is a very short period in a person's life, only seven years. But they are of constant importance as development continues. Psychological rehabilitation in cerebral palsy includes a system of special measures aimed at restoring (developing, forming) mental functions, processes, characteristics, abilities that allow the child to master and perform various actions. aimed at restoring (developing) social roles, adaptation in society, that is, psychological mechanisms of social integration.

The system of psychological rehabilitation consists of the following components: psychodiagnosis, psychocorrection, psychological support and referral to a psychological profession. The expediency of psychological rehabilitation, its priorities, optimal methodical techniques are determined primarily by which areas of mental activity are disturbed and which mental functions should be restored and developed first of all. This requires a psychodiagnostic examination. Psychodiagnostics allows to determine the current mental state and characteristics of potential mental development (zone of proxima). In other words, the development and formation of the child's personality is significantly affected by his exceptional position, which is related to the restriction of movement and speech, on the one hand; on the other hand, the attitude of the family to the child's illness, the environment around him. Therefore, you should always remember that the personality characteristics of children with cerebral palsy are the result of a close interaction of these two factors. It should be noted that parents can mitigate the social influence factor if they wish.

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